

Supporting Information for:

**Machine Learning-based Provenance Analysis of Portuguese Chalcolithic
Variscite: New Insights from n=170 Green Phosphate Beads.**

Sanchez-Gomez Daniel*¹, Odriozola Carlos ^{1,2}, Garrido-Cordero Jose Ángel^{1,2}, Ana Catarina Sousa¹

¹ University of Lisbon (UNIARQ), Lisbon, Portugal

² Universidad de Sevilla – Seville, Spain

*Corresponding author

Correspondence mail: daniel-sanchez-gomez@edu.ulisboa.pt

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Context of the sites studied:

Penha Verde - Quinta da Penha Verde:

This fortified settlement is located on a hill known as ‘Penha Verde’, on a formation of granite blocks on the northern face of the Sierra de Sintra. Its location and excavation was carried out in the 1950s by the Portuguese Geological Services (ZBYSZEWSKI y FERREIRA 1959) and recently reviewed by (J. L. Cardoso 2010). Although there are no general plans, the settlement is described with the presence of subcircular structures built with limestone slabs, specifically two circular houses, one of which preserved remains of a chimney, a silo partially excavated in the rock and a flagstone pavement that gives access to the house and surrounds the silo (C. Odriozola et al. 2013). The radiocarbon dating available for this settlement (J. L. Cardoso, 2010) places it in the second half of the 3rd millennium and the beginning of the 2nd millennium BCE, coinciding with the joint presence of “folha de acácia” and Bell Beaker ceramics. The beads analyzed (36 beads) come from the houses

mentioned (House 1 (7/36); House 2 (4/36)). The other materials (25/36) do not have a specific location within the settlement of Penha Verde (C. Odriozola et al. 2013).

Tholos do Barro - Monte da Pena:

a National Monument atop Monte da Pena (185m altitude), represents Portugal's largest and best-preserved false dome tomb. Discovered in 1909 by Paul Bovier-Lapierre and excavated by Félix Alves Pereira with Eugénio Jalhay, the collective burial comprises a 6-meter-diameter circular chamber with false dome construction, a 4-meter corridor, and a 13-meter concentric stone mound. The 1909 excavation yielded human remains, smooth polished pottery, polished stone axes, flint tools, archer's armguard, slate plaque, limestone betyls, decorated marble vessel fragment, approximately three dozen beads and pendants (greenstones, jasper, bone), and copper/bronze objects (fibula, pedunculated dagger, ring). Further interventions (2021-2022) revealed comprehensive architectural details, funerary deposits in chamber and corridor, and intense external symbolic activity including a partial entrance wall. From this assemblage, n=32 greenstone beads were analyzed.

Leceia:

Leceia is a fortified settlement in the Portuguese Extremadura region that occupies approximately 10,000 m² on a rocky platform with eastern and southern slopes in what is now the district of Lisbon, municipality of Oeiras. The defensive system comprises three arched walls with entrances connected by winding paths, featuring external semi-circular hollow bastions secondarily used as dwellings or storage, which were intensively excavated from the 1980s to the early 2000s (J. Cardoso 2011, 2022). A Bell Beaker hut exists outside the settlement. Occupied from the late Neolithic through the late Chalcolithic, the fortification represents three different occupation phases and five constructive phases spanning approximately a thousand years, between the last quarter of the 4th millennium BC and the last quarter of the 3rd millennium BC.

Material culture includes late Neolithic Extremaduran ceramics (serrated rims, carinated bowls), Chalcolithic pottery (fluted cups, acacia leaf-decorated vases, bell beakers), bone/stone/ ivory/metal artifacts, votive objects, human and faunal remains (including dogs, birds, fish,) (J. Cardoso 2010, 2020; J. Cardoso et al. 2014, 2020; J. Cardoso y Convertini 2022; J. L. Cardoso y Gibaja 2019). N=37 beads were analyzed.

Necrópole de Alcalar:

The Alcalar complex, located in Portimão, is one of the most prominent 3rd millennium BCE centres in southern Iberia. Spanning approximately 20 hectares, the site comprises a settlement with three defensive lines of moats, fences and walls, and the largest necropolis of tholoi in Portugal, with 18 monuments (Morán 2019; Sousa et al. 2024). Alcalar stands out for one of the highest concentrations of exotic prestige goods in the region—including variscite, Sicilian amber, ivory and gold—evidencing its role as a hub for long-distance exchange networks and wealth accumulation during the Chalcolithic.

Variscite beads have been recovered from multiple funerary contexts across the necropolis, totalling at least 84 pieces 65 of which are analysed in this work. Alcalar 4 (tholos) yielded the largest assemblage (n=40), where beads were found thanks to the careful sifting of extracted sediment, in direct association with amber, ivory and gold—the only context at the site combining all four prestige materials. Alcalar 3 (tholos) produced the second largest set (n=20), alongside amber and a significant deposit of copper artefacts interpreted as both utilitarian and prestige goods. Alcalar 2 (tholos) contained n=4 variscite beads along with a green silicate bead—notably the only monument where a non-variscite green bead was recorded. Smaller assemblages were documented in Alcalar 9 (tholos, n=2), where recent excavations revealed beads deposited directly on the crypt floor alongside bone remains and limestone beads before being sealed by a slate slab; Alcalar 8 (tholos, n=2); Alcalar 11 (tholos, n≥1); and Alcalar 1 (anta, n=1).

On the geochemical significance of XAI-derived feature importance see supplementary.

It is important to note that the approach adopted by VORTEX, which is based on the principles of information theory and game theory, identifies analytically significant elements—those that contribute most effectively to the discrimination of structured data—rather than establishing causal geochemical relationships. The rankings of feature importance and SHAP values are model-dependent and reflect the specific dataset and analytical protocol employed. However, when examining the resulting rankings in relation to the known geological and mineralogical contexts of the three Iberian deposits, a coherent geochemical logic emerges that validates the model's discrimination criteria and reveals features that previous approaches had overlooked:

For Gavá, the SHAP analysis identifies Ca, Sr, and Ba as the three most influential features (mean |SHAP| = 0.200, 0.081, and 0.070 respectively), forming a geochemically coherent triad. The Gavá Mines are hosted in Silurian shales adjacent to the Triassic dolomitic massif of Garraf, and the percolation of Ca-rich fluids derived from these dolomites promotes the precipitation of calcium-bearing phosphate phases — crandallite ($\text{CaAl}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), monetite, and planerite — that are documented at Gavá and absent from the other Iberian deposits (Manel Edo Benaiges et al. 1995; M. Edo Benaiges et al. 1998; Majado et al. 1995; C. P. Odriozola et al. 2016; Fábregas Valcarce y Rodríguez-Rellán 2019). The co-elevation of Sr and Ba is consistent with the well-established substitution of Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} for Ca^{2+} in phosphate crystal structures, reflecting a shared carbonate-hosted geochemical environment. None of these three elements featured in any previous discriminant scheme for variscite provenance. Additionally, Gavá's characteristically low V and Cr values — attributable to leaching from the host shales during diagenesis (Camprubí et al. 2003) — contribute to classification through their absence, distinguishing Gavá from the V- and Cr-enriched environments of Aliste and Encinasola.

For Aliste, the dominant features are As (0.130), Mo (0.076), V (0.061), and Cr (0.060), reflecting the organic matter-rich Silurian black shale formation environment documented at Palazuelo de las Cuevas (Moro Benito et al. 1995). The incorporation of arsenate [AsO_4] $^{3-}$, vanadate [VO_4] $^{3-}$, and chromate [CrO_4] $^{3-}$ into the phosphate lattice through the well-documented isotypism between these anions and [PO_4] $^{3-}$ (Moore 1984) is a consequence of reducing conditions in organic-rich sedimentary environments. VORTEX reveals that it is As — and not Cr — that is the most discriminating factor: for Aliste, low As values exert a strong negative SHAP influence (pushing predictions away from this source), whereas for Encinasola high As values drive a clear positive contribution. This contrast is geochemically coherent, as the Encinasola area hosts the highest As concentrations reported in the Iberian Peninsula (Cama et al. 2008), making elevated As a hallmark of that source rather than of Aliste. Furthermore, Mo, which was never considered in any prior provenance scheme, ranks as the second most important feature for Aliste; its prominence is geochemically coherent, as Mo–S complexes concentrated in organic-rich black shales under reducing conditions provide a formation-specific signature.

For Encinasola, the feature importance profile — Ca (0.104), V (0.077), As (0.076), K (0.070), Se (0.038) — shares V and As with Aliste among its top features but differs qualitatively through the prominence of K and Se. The SHAP plot shows that As exerts a bidirectional influence for Encinasola: high feature values push predictions strongly toward this source, while low values push them away, consistent with the exceptionally high natural As background of the Ossa-Morena Zone reported by Cama (2008). The elevated importance of K, attributable to K-bearing phyllosilicate phases (muscovite, sericite) in the host schists, is three times greater for Encinasola than for Aliste or Gavá. Se, enriched through the Cu–Se geochemical association characteristic of the polymetallic mineralisation context at Pico Centeno — the same context that supported later copper mining at the site — emerges as a diagnostic element for this source. Neither K nor Se was included in any prior discriminant framework.

In sum, five of the fifteen most important features across the three deposits — Mo, Sr, Ba, K, and Se — were entirely absent from all previous provenance models, including the most comprehensive rule-based scheme (G. Querré et al. 2019). All five have interpretable

geochemical explanations tied to deposit-specific formation environments: carbonate influence at Gavá, organic-rich reducing conditions at Aliste, and polymetallic schist-hosted mineralisation at Encinasola. This convergence between data-driven feature selection and established phosphate geochemistry suggests that XAI techniques, when applied to sufficiently large and representative compositional datasets, can function as proxys for geochemical investigation — surfacing elements whose discriminatory power operates in the high-dimensional interactions between multiple elements rather than in the individual elemental concentrations accessible through binary or ternary visualisations.

Dataset Description

GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Dataset title:

p-XRF Compositional Data of n=171 green phosphate prehistoric Artifacts from four Portuguese Archaeological Sites (Leceia, Penha Verde, Tholos do Barro and Necrópole de Alcalar)

2. Authorship:

Name: Daniel Sanchez-Gomez
Institution: Universidade de Lisboa (UNIARQ)
Email: daniel-sanchez-gomez@edu.ulisboa.pt
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3179-3288>

Name: Carlos P. Odriozola Lloret
Institution: Universidad de Sevilla
Email: codriozola@us.es
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4411-2528>

Name: José Angel Garrido-Cordero
Institution: Universidad de Sevilla
Email: jgarrido8@us.es
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9585-7917>

Name: Ana Caterina Sousa
Institution: Universidade de Lisboa (UNIARQ)
Email: sousa@edu.ulisboa.pt
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2709-3967>

DESCRIPTION

1. Dataset language:

ENG/ESP

2. Abstract:

This dataset includes the compositional information of n=171 samples of geoarchaeological green phosphate minerals from four Portuguese archaeological sites: Leceia, Penha Verde, Tholos do Barro and Necrópole de Alcalar. It has been used to establish the geological provenance using a novel machine learning-based framework called VORTEX.

3. Keywords:

Term: variscite (Getty Thesaurus)

Term: provenance analysis (Getty Thesaurus)

Term: machine learning (MeSH Thesaurus)

Term: Iberian Peninsula (Getty Thesaurus)

Term: p-XRF (Getty Thesaurus)

4. Date of data collection: 2011–2021

5. Historical period: IV Mil cal BCE – III Mil cal BCE

6. Publication Date: 2025-10-14

7. Grant Information:

Foundation for Science and Technology of Portugal FCT — UI/BD/154365/2023: Exploring a data-driven approach to study Social Complexity in Prehistory

Foundation for Science and Technology of Portugal FCT — UID/00698: Centre for Archaeology. University of Lisbon

Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación — PID2021-124421NB-I00: Arqueología de las falsificaciones y la percepción

9. Kind of data: Experimental data (p-XRF elemental composition, XRD mineralogical characterisation), Geospatial data

10. Alternative URL: https://github.com/Daniel-SanchezG/VORTEX_FINAL

ACCESS INFORMATION

Dataset DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19111672

Citation:

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Version: V3

METHODOLOGICAL INFORMATION

1. Methods:

Chemical composition was measured by an Oxford Instrument XMET-7500 p-EDX equipped with a Rh tube, a silicon drift detector (SDD), and an automatic 5-position filter changer. Mean analysis time per sample was 60s.

2. Quantification:

Quantification was obtained using the SOILS-LE program based on the fundamental parameter (FP) method (Beckhoff et al., 2006). Using updated atomic parameters with FP, calculated compositions agree within 1% for most elements with certified values (Elam et al., 2004).

3. Data processing:

All elements were converted into atomic percentages. Below detection limit values (BDL) were replaced with $LoD/\sqrt{2}$ (Croghan, 2003). LoD values for a SiO_2 matrix were converted from ppm to atomic percent (see pXRF_LoD sheet). Elements never detected in the archaeological dataset (Sc, Ga, Ge, Br, Y, Nb, Ru, W, Th) and elemental features detected in fewer than 10% of samples were removed, and the composition of each sample closed to 100% over 18 informative elements: (Al, Si, P, S, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, V, Cr, Fe, Cu, Zn, As, Sr, Zr, Mo, Ta)

4. Software:

Oxford Instrument XMET-7500 p-EDX software (SOILS-LE fundamental parameter) for data extraction. Data preprocessing performed using the xrf_preprocess.py Python module (numpy, pandas).

5. Calibration:

32-mm pellets of BCR-032#919 (Natural Moroccan phosphate standard, European Commission IRMM) were analyzed frequently during routines to ensure calibration accuracy. Raw measurements are provided in the (BCR-032#919)CRM sheet; instrument accuracy relative to certified values is documented in the Accuracy_CRM sheet; and descriptive statistics for raw (pre-closure) measurements are in the CRM_Stats sheet.

FILE OVERVIEW

Primary file: 20260319CAAProceedingsDatasetV3.xlsx

Multi-sheet Excel workbook containing raw data, processed data, predictions, provenance analysis, calibration data, and sensitivity analysis.

Formats: .csv, .xlsx, .docx

SPECIFIC INFORMATION FOR TABULAR DATA

The Excel workbook contains 10 sheets described below.

pXRF_rawData (n=171)

Feature	Type	Description
id	Primary Key —	

	sample identifier	
Site	String	Archaeological site (4 classes)
Structure	String	Archaeological structure or context
Duration	Float	p-XRF analysis time (seconds)
Al to Th	Float	Elemental concentrations in wt% (37 elements)
Al_sd to Th_sd	Float	Precision (standard deviation) for each element

Processed (n=171)

Feature	Type	Description
Name	String	Primary Key — sample identifier
Site	String	Archaeological site
Structure	String	Archaeological structure or context
duration	Float	p-XRF analysis time (seconds)
Al to Th	Float	Elemental concentrations in at%, closed to 100% (18 elements: Al, Si, P, S, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, V, Cr, Fe, Cu, Zn, As, Sr, Zr, Mo, Ta)
Σ	Float	Verification column — sum of all elements (must equal 100.0)

RawPredictions (n=170)

Feature	Type	Description
id	String	Primary Key
Site	String	Archaeological site
Prediction	String	Response variable — model prediction label (CT = Can Tintorer/Gavà; PCM = Pico Centeno/Encinasola; PDLC = Aliste)
prediction_score_CT	Float	Confidence value [0 to 1]
prediction_score_PCM	Float	Confidence value [0 to 1]
prediction_score_PDLC	Float	Confidence value [0 to 1]

ProvenanceAnalysis (n=4)

Feature	Type	Description
Site	String	Archaeological site (4 sites)

Samples_analyzed	Int	Number of samples analysed per site
Gavá	Int	Samples assigned to Gavá
Encinasola	Int	Samples assigned to Encinasola
Aliste	Int	Samples assigned to Aliste
Uncertain(%)	Float	Percentage of uncertain samples
Samples_for_provenance	Int	Effective samples for provenance
Median_entropy	Float	Intra-site uncertainty statistic
Consensus	String	Majority-vote provenance determination
Homogeneity	Float	Proportion [0–1] of majority source

pXRF_LoD (n=44)

Feature	Type	Description
Element	String	Chemical element symbol
Measure time	String	p-XRF measurement time (60s)
LoD ppm	Float	Limit of detection in ppm (SiO ₂ matrix)
LoD at%	Float	Limit of detection in atomic percent
LoD/√2	Float	Imputation value for BDL measurements (at%)

(BCR-032#919)CRM (n=45)

Feature	Type	Description
Name	String	Reference material identifier (BCR32)
Duration	Float	p-XRF analysis time (seconds)
Al, Si, P, ... W	Float	Measured elemental concentrations (at%)
+/-	Float	Precision for each element measurement

Accuracy_CRM

Instrument accuracy table comparing n=45 BCR-032#919 measurements (after LoD imputation and compositional closure to 100%) against certified reference values. Includes absolute and relative errors per element. Note: values in this sheet are post-closure and therefore not directly comparable to the raw (pre-closure) values in CRM_Stats.

CRM_Stats

Descriptive statistics (n detected, n total, mean, SD, RSD, min, Q25, median, Q75, max) for all elements measured on the BCR-032#919 reference material (n=45 measurements), reported as raw pre-closure atomic percentages. Note: these pre-closure values are not directly comparable to the post-closure values in Accuracy_CRM; the difference arises from

compositional closure and matrix-induced underestimation of light elements (Si, S) in the Ca-P-rich matrix of BCR-032.

SensitivityAnalysis (n=20)

Feature	Type	Description
Site	String	Archaeological site
Threshold	Float	Confidence threshold (0.60–0.80)
Total	Int	Total samples per site
Uncertain_n	Int	Samples flagged as uncertain
Uncertain_%	Float	Percentage of uncertain samples
Samples_Analyzed	Int	Effective samples after filtering

VORTEX_training_data (n=1818)

Geological reference dataset used to train the VORTEX Random Forest classifier (n=1,818 samples: Can Tintorer/Gavà n=857, PDLC/Aliste n=514, Pico Centeno/Encinasola n=447). Contains raw p-XRF elemental concentrations and associated metadata (mineralogy by XRD, publication status, source type). This sheet is provided for transparency and reproducibility; the full annotated dataset with DOI is also published separately in Sanchez-Gomez et al. (2025) (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2025.111961>).

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